

INTERFACE STUDY OF COMPOSITE BANDS FORMED BY POWDER PLATING AND ROLLING (PPR)

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SUMMARY: Different kinds of metal powder have been plated on a band of mild steel and then both of them rolled together. With this new method, some composite bands such as Cu-steel, Al-steel, Sn-steel, etc., have been made. TEM, EPMA, XPS and XRD are used to study the interface among powder particles, the boundary of grains inside powder particles and the interface between composite-layered and matrix. The metal powders are deformed by force and their surface areas increase two or three times. There exist some pieces of oxidation film at the interface between powder particles, and there is a lot of dislocation-substructures in the grain inside powder particles. The SADP changes into multiple spots or small arcs, and take on a form of a discontinuous ring distribution. After annealing, a diffusion phenomenon can be observed at the interface among powder particles and between composite-layer and matrix. Three conclusions are given.

KEYWORDS: metals composite, surface coating, powder processing, multi-layers interfaces, laminar materials

INTRODUCTION

It is well known that there are many methods for forming composite [1-3]. There also has been a lot of research focused on the structures and properties of composite [4-6]. PPR (Powder Plating and Rolling) is a new method for forming composite bands [7]. With PPR, which has been patented, metal powders (chosen as composite-layered metal) are plated onto the other metal band (chosen as the matrix) and then both of them are rolled together to obtain a composite band. In consideration of the difference of the presently reported technology from others, i.e. the composite-layered metal is not a sheet but powder, the interfaces of composite band formed by PPR are different from those of composites formed by other methods. In this paper, the main purpose is to study the interface among powder particles, the boundary of grain inside powder particles and the interface between the composite-layer and matrix. The effect of annealing temperature on the interface and microstructure of composite bands is also discussed. These will provide useful information for controlling the properties of composite in real production.

EXPERIMENT

Plating a mild-steel band with different kinds of metal powder, and then rolling them together, a system of composite bands, such as Cu-steel, Al-steel, Sn-steel can be prepared. For different metal powder, a variant of annealing temperatures are employed in a vacuum furnace. Cutting out the composite bands into pieces, the samples for observing microstructure of composite bands are ready.

By rubbing the matrix off the sample, transforming the composite-lamella into thin foils. The thin foils are prepared by the electrochemistry-polishing method and examined in TEM of 2000-EX with accelerating voltage of 200 kv.

Samples for observing in EPMA are prepared by the way the same with the sample for observing in OM and then the samples are examined in EPMA of EPMA505. Some samples are analyzed by using XPS and XRD.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Interfaces Among Powder Particles

Different from traditional composite materials, surface composite layer is an even substance formed of a multitude of metal powder particles that are elongated in all directions, one on the top of another in the deforming process. Therefore, there exist a large number of interfaces among particles. The binding at the interfaces is of importance. Before being pressed tight, powder particles with bigger diameter will begin to undergo a deformation while powder particles with smaller diameter will slide themselves into the gaps among the particles

Fig.1: Deforming process of metal powder particles

Fig. 2: TEM picture of the interfaces of aluminum powder particles

with bigger diameter. With deforming pressure increasing, powder particles will gradually flatten out, close to each other, the gaps becoming smaller and smaller (See Fig.1a). Finally, the powder particles overlap each other and combine into continuous lamella. The appearance shows that metal particles have been cold welded into an even and continuous thin layer covering the surface of the matrix metal (See Fig.1b). An analysis finds that the surface areas of metal powder particles expand two or three times after undergoing deformation. The oxidation film wrapping the metal powder particles bursts, exposing a lot of clean and non-

oxidation surfaces. It is these clean non-oxidation surfaces that enable the metal particles to weld together closely. Table 1 presents the statistics of the deformation of metal powder particles.

Fig.2 shows that the broken fragments of aluminum oxide film can be observed at the interfaces of aluminum powder particles.

Table 1: Statistics of the deformation of the metal powder particles

metal powder	original diameter (mm)	thickness after deformation (mm)	average diameter after deformation (mm)	average elongation rate (%)	increase rate of surface areas (%)
Al	0.079	0.01	0.185	134	174
Cu	0.055	0.005	0.149	170	267
Sn	0.055	0.005	0.152	176	282

Boundary of Grain Inside Powder Particle

It can know from the above analysis that metal powder particles undergo a considerably big deformation in the composite processing with PPR. During the composite processing, the grains inside powder particle undergo a considerably big deformation too. The result of XRD examination shows that the grain's size inside a powder particles is about 1200--1400 Å before deformation while the size becomes about 240--280Å after deformation. This shows that deformation affects a strong crushing function on metal grains. An observance reveals that there exist concentrated dislocation groups (See Fig.3a) inside grains. These dislocation lines tangle together, forming dislocation-substructures. The results of SADP can

Fig. 3: Dislocation line and SADP inside grains of copper powder particle

Fig. 4: Dislocation outcrop copper powder particle etched tanks at the interface of the dislocation-substructure inside grain

be seen in Fig.3(b), in which the diffraction spots change into multiple spots or small arcs, and take on a form of a discontinuous ring distribution. This means that the crystals inside the grains are crushed and been super-fineness under the large deformation forces, and these dislocation-substructures are of small phase difference in selected area. Fig.4 clearly shows the dislocation outcrop etched tanks at the interface of the dislocation-substructure inside the grain. After recrystallization annealing treatment, the original grain boundaries and dislocation line are hard to find under TEM. The substructure inside grain is replaced by annealing twin crystals or normal crystals (See Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

Fig. 5: Texture of copper grains after annealing Fig. 6: Texture of tin grains after annealing

Binding Interface Between Composite-Layer and Matrix Metal

By using XPS, the characteristic binding energy peaks of Cu and Al can be found at the binding surface of the steel matrix (See Fig.7 and Fig.8). The analysis results show that under a strong external force the powder particles and the matrix are made to be close to each other to atomic size, producing a metallic bond binding between them.

The observation about the composite bands which has undergone diffusion annealing with EPMA also reveals that the composite layer metal is closely bond with the matrix and the metal atoms on the both sides of the interface can cross the interface between powder composite layer and matrix by means of diffusion to form a diffusion bonding. Fig.9 and Fig.10 present the second electronic images of the Al-steel, Cu-steel composite bands by using EPMA. The results of a linear scanning show that there is a clear component gradient changes at the binding interface, which shows clearly that there is a diffusion occurring at the interface between the composite layer and the matrix under the diffusion annealing temperature but no metal compound is formed. An examination of the bonding strength of the interface also reveals the good bonding.

Fig. 7: XPS analytical spectrum line at the bonding surface of the steel matrix of aluminum-steel composite band

Fig. 8: XPS analytical spectrum line at the binding surface of the steel matrix of copper-steel composite band

Fig. 9 Binding interface of aluminum-steel band

Fig. 10: Binding interface of copper-steel composite band.

CONCLUSIONS

(1) In the preparation of PPR, the surface areas of metal powder particles increase two or three times, which makes the oxidation film of powder particles burst and fall down, exposing a lot clean and non-oxidation surface. It is these clean non-oxidation surfaces that ensure a bind among metal particles and between grain composite layer and matrix.

(2) After deformation, there exist much interfaces of powder particle inside composite layer and there exist much boundary inside grain in every powder particle. Therefore, it is important a good bind among the interfaces of powder particles and the boundaries of grains.

(3) A proper annealing treatment can make atoms spread cross the interface, thus causing the disappearance of the interfaces of powder particles which have overlapped each other, form an even continuous metal thin layer by recrystallizing. The dislocation-substructures inside grains is replaced by normal crystals. A diffusion bonding is formed at the interfaces between composite-layer and matrix through atomic diffusion.

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